

SOCIAL SCIENCES

INFORMATION SOCIETY AND INFORMATION SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA FOR 2021-2026

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054728>

Abstract

Cyberspace offers countless opportunities for economic development, social interaction and political cooperation, but also provides tools for illegal surveillance, personal data collection, influencing democratic processes, committing crimes and exchanging numerous ways and methods of warfare, which make cybercrime the most widespread form of transnational crime. Given that the aspiration and officially declared national strategic goal of the Republic of Serbia is to become a member state of the European Union, Serbia should resolve "all cyber issues" in accordance with the EU framework. This paper provides an overview of the Strategy for Information Society Development and Information Security in the Republic of Serbia for 2021-2026. This paper focuses on the provisions of the Strategy and the plans that Serbian stakeholders have for the development and protection of information systems in Serbia in all segments, as well as in the systems of special importance for the state. Special attention was given to the development of functional electronic systems in all areas of a public life, as well as to the definition of goals and desired changes that need to be implemented in Serbian legislation in the period 2021-2026.

Keywords: Information society, information security, digitalization, system of special importance

1. Introduction

The widespread use of information technology worldwide and in Serbia, in particular, is prone to a further intensive development. Information security is a crucial part of the cyber security, which refers exclusively to the processes and tools designed and deployed for data security, and for the protection of personal and professional information from modification, disruption, destruction, and inspection. The intention is to protect sensitive information from unauthorised activities through information security, and especially from possible theft of private information, data tampering, and data deletion.

Given that the Republic of Serbia is still at a relatively early stage of development of its comprehensive national framework governing cyber security, it is necessary to point out the existing legal framework, especially through the prism of relevant legal documents and through the importance of the recently adopted Strategy for Information Society Development and Information Security in the Republic of Serbia for 2021-2026.

2. Information security in cyberspace in Serbian legislation

In Europe, the fight against cybercrime began during the 90's and it was primarily based on relevant international documents. Since then, many countries have changed, modernised and coordinated their national criminal legislation, according to the documents that have been adopted at the international level [1].

The Republic of Serbia signed and ratified the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime no.185 of 2001 and the Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime concerning the criminalization of acts of a racist and xenophobic nature committed through computer systems on April 7, 2005 in Helsinki, as a member of the State Union of Serbia and Montenegro

(at that time), and the National Assembly of the Republic of Serbia ratified both documents in 2009 [2-3]. These documents represent the first international documents regulating the substantive, procedural, organisational and international framework for criminal offences committed via the Internet and computer networks.

At the national level, Serbia passed in 2016 the Law on Information Security of the Republic of Serbia [4] which deals with the security of ICT systems and the ICT systems of special importance. Regarding the regulations governing access to information security, risk analysis is mentioned in the Decree concerning a closer regulation of measures for the protection of ICT systems of special importance [5] but this Decree does not clearly define who is responsible for conducting a risk assessment and how comprehensive that assessment should be.

3. Information security in Strategies for information society and information security development in the Republic of Serbia until 2021

The importance of information society development was recognized in the Republic of Serbia more than a decade ago, when the first Strategy for Information Society Development in the Republic of Serbia until 2020 [6] was adopted. This Strategy was covering all priority areas that contribute to the information society development: electronic communications, governance, e-health and e-justice, ICT in education, science and culture, e-commerce, ICT business sector, information security. Information security, which was covered as one of the topics in this Strategy, has become extremely important in the previous period, since the use of new technologies has increased the risks that arise as a result.

The Strategy of Information Society Development adopted in 2010 aimed at developing the information

society and the exploitation the potential of information and communication technologies, in order to increase work efficiency, economic growth, and a higher employment rate and to raise the quality of life for all citizens of the Republic of Serbia. One of the goals was also to build and support an open, accessible and high-quality Internet access and, thus, to develop e-business, including: e-government, e-commerce, e-justice, e-health and e-education.

In 2017 the Government of the Republic of Serbia adopted the Strategy of Information Security Development for the period from 2017 to 2020 [7] which defined the principles of information security, priority areas and strategic goals related to the security of citizens, economy and state. This document is cross-sectoral and relevant for its development as strategic document in the field of new generation networks, digital skills, artificial intelligence, industrial policy development, smart specialisations, tourism, culture, agriculture, justice, high-tech crime, as well as regulations regarding electronic documents, electronic identification and trust services, information security and e-government, and children safety on the Internet.

The Strategy of Information Security Development adopted in 2017 aimed at developing and improving the information security in the Republic of Serbia and maintaining it at an adequate level by raising the level of security of information and communication systems, combating cybercrime and improving the information security of national importance.

4. The Strategy for Information Society Development and Information Security in the Republic of Serbia for 2021-2026

The Strategy for Information Society Development and Information Security in the Republic of Serbia for 2021-2026 [8] (hereafter: the Strategy) is also a cross-sectoral strategy which determines the goals and measures for the development of the information society and information security. The Strategy consists of nine areas of interest: description of the current situation, vision and desired changes, general and specific objectives, a mechanism for implementing the Strategy and method of reporting on implementation results as well as description of the negotiation with stakeholders during the writing of the Strategy, assessment of financial resources and analysis of financial effects, action plan for the implementation of the Strategy in the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2021 to 2026, the final part and the Action Plan for the period from 2021 to 2023.

Within the description of the current situation in the Republic of Serbia, the Strategy referred to the previously adopted two strategies and their implementation, but also describes the use of ICT in Serbia and the acquisition of e-skills. Special attention is given to the creation of services such as e-government, e-justice, e-education, e-health, e-culture, e-business, e-commerce, e-tourism, e-construction, e-agriculture, e-mining and e-energy. The principles of information security in general are also highlighted, with special emphasis on the information security of citizens, the economy sector and systems of special importance.

The Strategy has its general goal, which is achieved through three specific goals. The general goal of the Strategy is to develop an information society and electronic administration in the service of citizens and the economy, and to improve the information security of citizens, public administration and the economy. Special goals are the improvement of digital knowledge and skills of citizens, raising the capacity of public and private sector employees to use new technologies and the improvement of digital infrastructure in educational institutions, digitization of services and business in both public and private sector and the improvement of information security of citizens, public administration and the economy.

The use of ICT has become an integral part of every citizen, member of public administration and the economy sector, and it greatly affects everyday life, as well as the economy and the entire business sector. In that sense, it is necessary to adapt to the changes that the use of ICT brings and to focus on maximising the benefits that it allows us.

The basic changes that are to be achieved are:

1) The existence of a digitalized public administration that will efficiently and transparently provide services to citizens and the economy;

2) Higher level of digital skills for all citizens who can freely use ICT, both for everyday life and for communication with public administration;

3) Transformation of the economy, through the implementation of digitalization, in order to support the application of information technology for the purpose of modernising business in all industries;

4) The existence of an information and security environment with a sufficient level of risk awareness but also the benefits that new technologies provide to citizens, public administration and the economy.

The Strategy is focused on the development of public administration (e-government), especially through the sectors related to (1) e-justice, e-education, e-health and e-culture; (2) e-business, e-commerce and e-tourism; (3) e-construction, e-agriculture; (4) e-mining and e-energy; (5) ICT sector, but also through the information security of citizens, economic entities and ICT systems of special importance.

Much attention in the Strategy has been paid to the development of the eGovernment portal, which provides numerous services by several different institutions: (1) The Office of Information Technology and e-Government (applications like: *Bebo dobrodošla na svet, Lokalna poreska administracija, Produženje registracije vozila na ovlašćenim tehničkim pregledima, Prijava boravišta stranca, Zahtev za izdavanje uverenja o (ne)kažnjavanju* etc.); (2) The Ministry of the Interior Affairs (applications like: *eZakazivanje, Zamena isprava o oružju/predaja oružja* etc.); (3) The Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development (applications like: *eDnevnik, eUpis*); (3) (e)Dnevnik, eUpis - Electronic enrolment of student champions); (4) The Republic Health Insurance Fund (request for health issuance, request for a medicinal products for human use for which the Agency has issued a marketing authorization, request for a medicinal products for veterinary use for which the Agency has

issued a marketing authorization for medicine, request for a medical devices); (5) The Agency for Medicinal Products and Medical Devices of Serbia (like search of drugs for use in human medicine, search of certificates of drugs for use in veterinary medicine, open data on approved clinical trials, open data on generic names of medical devices etc.); (6) The e-Birth Registers (for cities of Loznica, Valjevo, Sremska Mitrovica and Niš). In order to further develop these services, the Strategy stated that the key challenge for the successful digital transformation of public administration in the Republic of Serbia is the foundations that will enable the implementation of planned measures in all segments of public administration which would enable efficient and coordinated functioning of the system.

The importance of e-justice is also recognized by the Justice Development Strategy for the period 2020-2025. [9] through the specific goal "Development of e-Justice", which provides plans for further improvement of e-services within the judiciary and legal system, which would provide access to justice, increase the quality of proceedings and decision-making, efficient case management, statistical monitoring and reporting on the work of court and the transparency of the work of judicial bodies. The strategy also states that the application of modern ICT, standardised software and centralised case management systems in courts and prosecutors' offices is necessary in order to realise some of the key principles of an effective judiciary system: independence, impartiality, accountability, expertise, efficiency and transparency. Therefore, the continuous development of the e-justice system is necessary, as a mechanism that contributes to the achievement of all strategic goals. The Judicial Information System was launched at the end of 2017, which enabled the electronic exchange of data between judicial bodies and courts, judicial professions and other state institutions. Through the judicial information system, all courts, public prosecutor's offices, public notaries and bailiffs can electronically check data from various registers and records kept by the competent institutions.

When it comes to the e-education, the fact that the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development has a Sector for Digitization in Education and Science speaks of the importance of digitalization, mainly through the use of electronic education systems in high schools and the establishment of 10,000 digital classrooms in Serbia.

One of the main priorities of the Government is the digitalization of the health care system, since this system is recognized as one of the most complex and important systems, especially during the COVID 19 pandemic. The past period provided health institutions with possibilities like e-medical prescription, e-radiology, e-portal for the patients, electronic health card, e-platform for telephone consultations with doctors etc.

Through digitalization in culture sector, the process of digitalization of cultural heritage should be systematically regulated and the resources of cultural institutions for the implementation of this process should be strengthened. Special attention will be paid to the digitization of archives and the creation of e-archives,

improving the work of unique software solutions in culture like the protection of cultural property, but also in the field of contemporary art.

The legislative framework governing e-commerce consists of three different legal documents: the Commerce Act [10], the E-Commerce Act [11] and the Consumer Protection Act [12]. The new Commerce Act was passed in 2019, and it regulates electronic commerce in the Republic of Serbia. This Act introduces for the first time the terms "electronic store" and "online platform", as well as the business model of sales "dropshipping". A significant legal novelty refers to the introduction of the "mystery shopper" institute, which authorizes the inspector to make a covert purchase in case of reasonable suspicion that the trade is unregistered, and thus provide evidence for this criminal act.

Concerning e-tourism, the Tourism Development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2016 to 2025 [13] was adopted in 2016 and, within the analysis of the current situation, stated that during the implementation of the previous Strategy failed in insufficient use of opportunities and benefits of information and communication technologies, Internet, social networks and platforms for the promotion of the tourist offer of the Republic of Serbia, as well as platforms for the development of new small and medium enterprises and their services. Accordingly, the objectives of the Tourism Development Strategy are: to improve and harmonise the methodology and procedures for the collection and processing of statistical data with international standards and practices. It is assumed that the realisation of these activities will result in achieving the digitalization of tourism and hospitality by introducing modern technologies in both businesses and the public sector.

When it comes to the field of e-construction, in the previous period a big progress was made in the area of electronic building permits. The introduction of an electronic system for issuing the construction permits represents one of the most important reform challenges. The key effects of establishing software for issuing electronic building permits are: faster and cheaper obtaining permits and conducting all permit procedures in one place. It is necessary to further improve the software that will enable faster and easier issuance of e-documents for construction by introducing new functionalities and upgrading the existing ones, based on the expressed needs of system users and analysis of issuing e-documents.

The Strategy for the Development of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2014-2024. [14], as one of the activities promulgate the development of all types of analytical information systems for agricultural support, including the missing parts of agricultural statistics, public reporting and forecasting systems, market information, registers, etc.

Digitization programs are also planned for the e-mining and e-energy sectors.

5. Information security in the Strategy for Information Society Development and Information Security in the Republic of Serbia for 2021-2026

With the development of new technologies and services that are increasingly provided electronically, there is a growing need to raise the level of information security. The concept of information security in the Strategy is primarily focused on information security of ICT systems of special importance, but it is also an important segment for both citizens and the economy, and awareness of its importance is growing. However, the risks of information security exist both on the side of the state and the ICT system of special importance, and on the side of citizens and the economy who are the first to be hit by high-tech crime.

When it comes to information security of citizens, the Strategy unequivocally links digital competencies and information security and the need to raise awareness and knowledge about them. Special attention is on information security of children, in terms of implementing protective measures through the activities of the National Contact Centre for Child Safety on the Internet, which aims to prevent and to raise awareness and knowledge about the benefits and risks of using the Internet and safe use of the Internet.

Considering the information security of the economy, it was stated that there is a significant space for improvement, and that measures should be focused on small and medium enterprises in the area of employee capacity, or in raising awareness meaning that the information security must be a part of everyone's business, regardless of the size of the company or the activity of work, and for the prevention and protection in case of incidents.

Information security of information systems that are recognized as ICT systems of special importance, and which must therefore be adequately protected, requires, in accordance with the Strategy, the application of technical, organisational and personnel measures, as well as other legal obligations related to incident reporting, submission of statistical data, regular audit of ICT systems, etc. These challenges also exist in ICT systems of special importance, which belong to the group of ICT systems that perform activities of general interest and mostly belong to a private sector (finance, energy, telecommunications, etc.), but are certainly less as the risks of incidents in these systems can have consequences, both financial and those related to the providing of services to a larger population, so the awareness of these systems is at a higher level and have a greater support from management in the application of protection measures.

6. Conclusion

By adopting the Law on Information Security with all related bylaws, as well as by adopting the national Strategy for Information Security Development and the accompanying Action Plan, the Republic of Serbia has certainly made progress towards establishing a comprehensive cyber security framework. It is now necessary to review the existing normative framework, in terms of eliminating all currently existing inconsistencies and shortcomings, as well as to truly understand the benefits of full harmonisation with existing principles,

standards and practices, primarily within the European Union.

Given the many opportunities and possibilities which are open to the Republic of Serbia regarding the establishment and strengthening of the national framework for cyber security through the use of membership and engagement in and with various regional and international organisations, as well as to their relatively low utilisation, implementation should be considered through awareness-raising programs and campaigns, through the establishment of more efficient mechanisms for informing stakeholders about opportunities and by providing support and guidance for applying and using these opportunities for capacity building and / or establishing channels of international cooperation with colleagues around the world. [15]

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